

Deliverable 6.1

Communication, dissemination and exploitation plan

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Project Executive Summary

The EU-funded 'Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environment' (PHOEBE) project aims to develop an integrated, dynamic human-centred predictive safety assessment framework in urban areas. This will be achieved by bringing together the interdisciplinary power of traffic simulation, road safety assessment, human behaviour, mode shift and induced demand modelling and new and emerging mobility data.

Focused on vulnerable road users' safety, the 3.5-year-long PHOEBE project will draw inspiration from real-world scenarios in the three pilot cities of Athens (GR), Valencia (ES) and West Midlands (UK). Testing activities will be performed across the use cases to simulate and forecast the impact of changes on safety in different scenarios of disruptions or transitions across urban transport networks.

Predicting and visualising the safety and socioeconomic outcomes of new forms of transport, new technologies, or regulatory and behavioural changes from the individual (micro) level up to the network-wide (macro) level will also be a significant game-changer for urban stakeholders. The results of PHOEBE can be used as a blueprint by other European cities to develop their knowledge products, such as socioeconomic analysis model, urban road safety assessment, human behaviour and choice modelling.

PHOEBE pilot cities

List of participating cities:

- Athens (Greece)
- Valencia (Spain)
- West Midlands (United Kingdom)

Social Links:

https://twitter.com/Project_PHOEBE

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/phoebe-project/>

<https://www.youtube.com/@phoebeproject>

For further information please visit WWW.PHOEBE-PROJECT.EU

Project Partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
EVROPSKI INSTITUT ZA OCENJEVANJE CEST - EURORAP	SI	EIRA
ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	EL	NTUA
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	NL	TUD
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE	TUM
AIMSUN SLU	ES	AIM
POLIS AISBL	BE	POLIS
FACTUAL CONSULTING SL	ES	FC
UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	UPV
OSEVEN SINGLE MEMBER PRIVATE COMPANY	EL	O7
THE FLOW LIMITED	UK	FLOW
INTERNATIONAL ROAD ASSESSMENT PROGRAMME	UK	iRAP

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ASAP	As Soon As Possible
B2B	Business-to-business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
MS	Milestone
KER	Key Exploitable Result

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Deliverable executive summary

The 'Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan' is PHOEBE's guiding document for all communication and dissemination activities. It also includes an initial exploitation strategy. The plan lays out the framework and actions to achieve the WP6' Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation' objectives and will be crucial for the effective promotion and sustainability of PHOEBE outcomes. It describes the key messages, target audiences, and when and where communication and dissemination activities need to occur, whether per partner or jointly among partners or the consortium. It links with the other PHOEBE WPs and describes how it will support them and vice-versa, with guidelines for partners on their respective responsibilities and actions to be carried out for effective communication and dissemination. The plan also describes the project's visual identity, designed to brand the activities and outcomes of the project.

This is a living document that will change and adapt as PHOEBE activities evolve and will be updated accordingly.

Progress beyond the state of the art and play

Following PHOEBE objectives, its communication, dissemination and exploitation will be project long and collaborative effort. For such, the strategy intent to not only support the partners to fulfill the set KPIs, but also foster and consolidate a workframe of informing, promoting and communicating PHOEBE's activities, actions and results.

The strategy provide guidelines, tools, and a timeline so that all consortium partners can incorporate dissemination and communication in their daily work within PHOEBE, which will give a good base for the exploitation phase. Partners can check with whom to colabarate internally, whom to reach externally and profit from the dynamic digital and on-line dissemination environment, while having clear the messages and a consistent project narrative. A consistent project narrative will increase the outreach and reinforce PHOEBE's benefits beyond the project timeline.

1 Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation Objectives

To maximise the impact of PHOEBE during its lifetime and beyond, the main objectives of WP6, which POLIS Network guides as the WP leader, are:

1. To maximise the impact of the project through targeted and measurable communication and dissemination activities;
2. To raise awareness of PHOEBE’s results and transfer knowledge to relevant stakeholders;
3. To guarantee that stakeholders and users of the project tools have a basic understanding of the PHOEBE framework and how it operates;
4. To ensure the broad applicability of the results, considering regulations and standards;
5. To ensure the most efficient exploitation of results, with amplified interaction with stakeholders and potential users to obtain feedback to enhance the exploitation opportunities;
6. To foster the exploitation of PHOEBE framework and tools beyond the project’s lifetime based on suitable business models and exploitation pathways;
7. To enhance coordination and synergies between PHOEBE and other EU-funded related projects and national programmes to maximise the joint impact.

1.1 Project Milestones and WPs links

The actions listed in this plan require a joint effort of all PHOEBE partners, either by providing input for activities coordinated by POLIS or by performing activities themselves. In addition, PHOEBE partners should be attentive to where project activities interact with external actors (e.g. local stakeholders in the WP4 pilots) as communication and dissemination activities may also be relevant.

For some project milestones and public deliverables, the communication and dissemination effort would increase to emphasise PHOEBE’s progress and work. Below in Table 1 and Figure 1 is an overview of the already identified effort points for communication and dissemination that will include significant content to be shared. Throughout the project and in collaboration with all the partners, other communication and dissemination effort points might be included or altered, as they are not limited to the ones listed here. For example, the internal deliverables with sensitive content, the responsible partners can decide if any relevant content can be shared with the public. If so, appropriate communication and dissemination activities can take place. In addition, PHOEBE’s own events and other relevant events will also generate effort points for communication and dissemination.

Communication and dissemination are dynamic activities and should follow the project work organically and regularly. The effort points are just highlights of these activities, and any necessary adjustments are expected as the project evolves.

Month	Project Deliverable or Milestone	WP
M6	D1.1 - SoA and end user needs review	WP1
M12	D1.2 - Theoretical principles and methodological approach of the PHOEBE framework and selection of tools	WP1

	D4.1 - Use case experimental designs	WP4
	MS2 - Methodological framework and technical specifications defined	WP1
M18	MS4 - Traffic simulation environments prepared for use cases	WP3
M30	MS5 - PHOEBE simulation and modelling results validated	WP3
M32	D4.2 - Consolidated use case evaluation and assessment report	WP4
	MS6 - Use case results available for extrapolation to the network-wide level	
M40	D5.1 - Consolidated PHOEBE framework methodology, network-level demonstration results and tools	WP5
	MS7 - Dynamic road safety assessment models and software released	
M44	D5.2 - User interface and implementation	WP5
	MS8 - PHOEBE framework user interface launched	
M45	End of the project	All
	Exploitation	

Table 1 - Project’s Public Deliverables and Milestone relevant to Communication and Dissemination

Figure 1 - Communication and Dissemination effort points

2 Summary of the PHOEBE project

A standardised project description (both long and short versions) is provided for project partners to assist with dissemination. All partners should use these consistently to avoid miscommunication and accelerate communication with external stakeholders.

Long Version

Urban traffic systems are increasingly dynamic. They are regularly ‘disrupted’ by new means of transport, new infrastructure, new technologies, and regulatory and behavioural changes. This presents challenges for transport managers in planning for these changes, as well as in achieving the ambitious target of zero road deaths and serious injuries by 2050.

Cities need new approaches to planning and managing mobility networks that account for the dynamic and rapidly changing nature of urban traffic environments. Central to this is safety—for all types of road users, gender, age and mobility levels.

The EU-funded Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environment consortium (known as Project PHOEBE) brings together the inter-disciplinary power of traffic simulation, road safety assessment, human behaviour, modal shift and induced demand modelling and mobility data into a harmonised, prospective assessment framework for road safety.

The PHOEBE framework will bring together research, data and innovative tools and models to simulate and forecast the safety impact of disruptive changes, transitions or scenarios across urban transport networks, with a particular focus on vulnerable road users' safety. The 3.5-year-long PHOEBE project will apply and refine the framework in real-world scenarios across three pilot cities, Athens (GR), Valencia (ES) and West Midlands (UK).

The predictive and visualisation capabilities to be delivered by Project PHOEBE will be a significant game-changer for urban stakeholders, helping mobility planners, designers and managers understand the impacts of changes from the individual level up to the network-wide level. The PHOEBE framework will be available to other European cities as a blueprint for them to understand and evaluate the long-term safety, mode choice and socioeconomic impacts of changes before they are made.

Short Version

Cities need new approaches to planning and managing mobility networks that account for the dynamic and rapidly changing nature of urban traffic environments. Central to this is safety—for all types of road users, gender, age and mobility levels. The EU-funded Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environment consortium (known as Project PHOEBE) brings together the inter-disciplinary power of traffic simulation, road safety assessment, human behaviour, modal shift and induced demand modelling and mobility data into a harmonised, prospective assessment framework for road safety. The 3.5-year-long PHOEBE project will apply and refine the framework in real-world scenarios across three pilot cities, Athens (GR), Valencia (ES) and West Midlands (UK). The PHOEBE framework will be available to other European cities as a blueprint for them to understand and evaluate the long-term safety, mode choice and socioeconomic impacts of changes before they are made.

3 Key Messages and Target Groups

3.1 Key Messages

Based on the objectives set by the project and to ensure that its relevance extends beyond the project partners and timeline, PHOEBE has established key messages based on the objectives set by the project. These key messages will guarantee a consistent communication of the project's narrative and support the communication and dissemination objectives.

PHOEBE's key messages are as follows:

- Highlight the characteristics of PHOEBE's safety assessment methodological framework and modules and the advantages of its dynamic framework for city and regional transport authorities and simulation developers operating in the traffic sector
- Emphasise PHOEBE's objectives towards safer urban environments and its foreseen benefits and impacts, including how it will help cities achieve a 50% reduction in road deaths and serious injuries by 2050
- Frame PHOEBE's relevance and need under the context of traffic models for road safety predictions
- Underline the importance of PHOEBE's dynamic safety assessment methodological framework to reduce crashes, traffic accidents and injuries
- Underscore PHOEBE's framework transferability and reach potential
- Underline PHOEBE's focus on socioeconomic components and outcomes

These above-stated key messages will be appropriately modified to speak to the various target audience PHOEBE seeks to engage. The chosen communication tool and the channel will also influence the tone and content.

Table 2 below- Project’s Public Deliverables and Milestone relevant to Communication and Dissemination gives an overview of the key messages that could be more relevant during the effort points (Table 1 and Figure 1) to disseminate and communicate the specific outcomes and the key messages that relate to the project’s overall goals.

Month of effort (per Table 1)	Key Message
M6, M12, M40, M44, M45	Highlight the characteristics of PHOEBE’s safety assessment methodological framework and modules and the advantages of its dynamic framework for city and regional transport authorities and simulation developers operating in the traffic sector
Throughout the project	Emphasise PHOEBE’s objectives towards safer urban environments and its foreseen benefits and impacts, including how it will help cities achieve a 50% reduction in road deaths and serious injuries by 2050
Throughout the project	Frame PHOEBE’s relevance and need under the context of traffic models for road safety predictions
M6, M12, M40	Underline the importance of PHOEBE’s dynamic safety assessment methodological framework to reduce crashes, traffic accidents and injuries
M6, M12, M44, M45	Underscore PHOEBE’s framework transferability and reach potential
Throughout the project	Underline PHOEBE’s focus on socioeconomic components and outcomes

Table 2 - Key Messages Relevant to PHOEBE’s timeline

3.2 Target Groups

PHOEBE adopts an interdisciplinary approach to deal with a multidisciplinary problem: mobility safety. Therefore, the project will need to reach different actors in the European context throughout and beyond its timeline.

Six main target audiences have been identified and are listed below. The outcomes of PHOEBE should positively impact the target groups mentioned below, either within their work practices, product developments or daily life. However, at the moment of writing, some of these target groups need to be either identified or further specified - this will be done throughout the project. Thus, the list of target groups is not exhaustive and will be nourished.

PHOEBE’s key target groups identified so far are as follows:

A. Authorities

Local and regional public administrations, transport authorities, public administrations, local and regional policymakers, local and regional decision makers

Local and regional authorities are key in employing PHOEBE’s framework and managing the necessary resources for that to take place. The local and regional level is also where the benefits of PHOEBE work can be concretely perceived.

B. Private sector

Traffic simulation providers, data providers, mobility-sector service providers, infrastructure and logistic providers

The private sector interested in transport safety has a role to play via enhanced or enabled new road safety risk estimation products.

C. Academia and Researchers

Universities, Research Institutes and researchers

Academia and researchers dealing with the application and piloting of new safety assessment methods, as well as training and education, will play a key role in guaranteeing that future users will understand how the PHOEBE framework works and how to use it.

D. Professionals

Simulation developers operating in the traffic sector, urban mobility planners, road safety practitioners, mobility and modelling experts, European and national associations

PHOEBE’s framework will influence the work practice of the different professionals working with the different aspects of road safety assessment.

E. EU and global actors

High-level policymakers and decision makers, initiatives, committees and institutions

PHOEBE can influence and interact with EU and global level actors promoting safety road methodologies and protocols in an exchange of knowledge and beneficial practices for all sides.

F. Civil society

Safety-related road user interest groups, associations and organisations, especially for VRUs and media

Civil society will be positively impacted in their daily life by the possible outcomes of PHOEBE’s framework. User groups, NGOs, and citizens may act as trusted parties to support the design of new policies and procedures in addition to their prominent roles as information providers and advocates for safer urban streets.

Additionally, PHOEBE will build a multi-stakeholder engagement network that will be described in section 5.3. Fortunately, different project partners already have established connections and relations with several actors of the identified target groups, which will be utilised to communicate results. Nevertheless, the correct message and communication channels will ensure that the target groups are addressed accordingly and appropriately.

Objectives	Target Group					
	A	B	C	D	E	F
To maximise the impact of the project through targeted and measurable communication and dissemination activities	x	x	x	x	x	x
To raise awareness, inform PHOEBE’s results and transfer knowledge to relevant stakeholders	x	x	x	x	x	x
To guarantee that stakeholders and users of the project have a basic understanding of the PHOEBE framework and how it operates	x		x	x		
To ensure the broad applicability of the results, considering regulations and standards	x	x		x	x	
To ensure the most efficient exploitation of results, with amplified interaction with stakeholders and potential users to obtain feedback to enhance the exploitation opportunities	x	x	x	x	x	
To foster the exploitation of PHOEBE framework and tools beyond the project’s lifetime based on suitable business models and exploitation pathways		x		x		
To enhance coordination and synergies between the PHOEBE project and other EU-funded related projects and national programmes to maximise the joint impact	x		x		x	

Table 3 - PHOEBE communication matrix

4 Communication Channels and Tools

4.1 Visual Identity

Creating an appealing visual identity that is carried consistently throughout all communication materials will help target audiences recognise and identify PHOEBE. Branding and visual identity can significantly increase a project's communication potential.

Therefore, deliverables, presentations and any other products from PHOEBE (e.g. video, publications, manuals) should adhere to the project's visual identity.

The logo and colour scheme were developed to invoke positive, alert and safety sensations by using a bright and warm colour palette and a contrasting colder blue tone. Whereas the primary colours of blue and green are mostly associated with digitisation and decarbonisation, warmer colours such as yellow, orange and red are associated with cooperation and safety.

Additionally, a different version of the logo with an extended description of the project was also developed. This version can be used where the logo size can be bigger or in situations where a more explicit project description is needed. Both versions were also produced in grayscale, suited for economic printed materials.

Figure 2 - PHOEBE logo variations

All PHOEBE material should also include the acknowledgement of EU and UKRI funding.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101076963.

UK participants in Horizon Europe Project PHOEBE are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10038897 (The International Road Assessment Programme – iRAP) and 10056912 (The Flow)

Figure 3 - EU and UKRI funding acknowledgement

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4.1.1 Colour palette

The PHOEBE project partners shall use the following colour palette that is reflected in the project logo and visual identity.

	CMYK	RGB	HEX
	59/35/0/47	56/88/136	385888
	85/25/0/35	25/126/167	197EA7
	66/57/0/55	40/50/116	283274
	0/16/100/0	255/215/0	FFD700
	0/35/100/0	255/165/0	FFA500
	0/73/100/0	255/69/0	FF4500
	0/91/73/14	220/20/60	DC143C
	0/0/0/50	128/128/128	808080

Figure 4 - Colour palette

4.1.2 Templates for documents and presentations

In order to guarantee the timely submission of PHOEBE deliveries and presentations in a uniform and branded format, different templates were created. PHOEBE has templates for deliverables, participant list, meeting agenda, press release and presentations. All templates will be available in the project drive so partners can use them as needed.

Title

Name of Presenter

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 1010759630

UK participants in Horizon Europe Project PHOEBE are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10038897 (The International Road Assessment Programme - IRAP) and 10056912 (The E3000)

Figure 5 - PHOEBE presentations template

Deliverable X.X

Name of deliverable

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 1010759630

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Figure 6 - PHOEBE deliverables template

4.2 Press Releases

Press releases are crucial to establishing a communication channel with PHOEBE's target Group F, civil society. The press releases will inform the general media about the project and raise public awareness by providing information regarding the project's key activities and how the PHOEBE safety assessment framework works. The *key message* that press releases will convey is to *emphasise PHOEBE's objectives towards safer urban environments and its foreseen benefits and impacts, including how it will help cities achieve a 50% reduction in road deaths and serious injuries by 2050 and underline PHOEBE's focus on socioeconomic components and outcomes.*

To build a strong relationship with specialised media and guarantee the publication of project-related news items, a total of six press releases will be written and timed to coincide with significant project moments (as per Table 1 and Figure 1).

Partners involved in the use cases are encouraged to communicate with the local press to inform their end users and citizens about the progress and value of the use cases.

PHOEBE's first press release communicated the project's kick-off meeting and was shared on 15 December 2022.

Figure 7 - PHOEBE's first Press release

4.3 Newsletter

As part of the digital presence of PHOEBE, e-newsletters will be developed and distributed during the project. The intended frequency of the newsletter is two per year, but more relevant than frequency, it also should be coupled with appropriate project milestones. Therefore, the content should be coherent and engaging to maintain the target audience's interest and will be linked with PHOEBE's website articles.

The newsletters should communicate the latest news about the projects, intermediate results, and announcements of workshops, events and other activities. POLIS is responsible for producing the newsletters, but input should come from all partners.

The sign-up form for PHOEBE's newsletter has been made easy-to-find on the project's website and has the potential to reach most of the identified target groups.

4.4 Website

The project website, which is accessible through <http://www.phoebe-project.eu> is the main access point to all key information about the project, its results and regular updates, which include regular news items and event invitations. Furthermore, the homepage is the project's main repository, which consists of all publicly available deliverables in a dedicated library. It is also the information hub that allows interested stakeholders to engage with PHOEBE through a dedicated newsletter submission form, direct links to the social media accounts (see section 4.5 Social Media), and additional visual media content. In addition to the elements related to the content repository, the following aspects are important:

- Overview of project partners:
Includes a map indicating the project partners' location and direct links to the respective organisations and academic institutions.
- Overview of sister projects:
The two 'sister projects' awarded in the same call are highlighted on a dedicated sub-page to enhance cooperation.
- Leaflet:
To facilitate the dissemination of the project and allow stakeholders to gain an overview, the project leaflet is prominently featured across the homepage, thanks to direct links to download the PDF.

Overall, the aim of the community of interested stakeholders to promote interaction and interest in PHOEBE safety is guaranteed, thanks to the page's various features, which are updated regularly.

Figure 8 - PHOEBE website homepage – design draft

4.5 Social Media

Social media is crucial for communicating and disseminating PHOEBE to a wider audience. Using social media efficiently will support PHOEBE in enhancing its reach and building a reputation and awareness of the project and its outcomes.

PHOEBE's activities, news and main results will be promoted through its own social media accounts (mainly LinkedIn and Twitter) as well as through each partner's own communication accounts. POLIS will manage PHOEBE's LinkedIn and Twitter accounts, creating content and maintaining a consistent presence and language. POLIS will also encourage partners to reproduce and adapt posts to their own channels in cooperation with the remaining partners. Furthermore, since photos and updates from the pilots are often the most tangible and relatable results that interest a wider audience, pilot city partners shall provide regular updates about the progress in the three PHOEBE pilot cities.

The strategic objectives of PHOEBE's social media presence are to:

- Dynamically reach a broad audience, enabling an interactive dialogue with relevant stakeholders.
- Give an informal voice to PHOEBE.
- Attract traffic to PHOEBE's website.
- Complement traditional communications channels, e.g. printed publications, events, press outreach and targeted mailings.
- Monitor mentions of PHOEBE, project partners, project outcomes and other important activities.
- Provide on-site and live coverage of key events, such as conferences or speaking engagements of PHOEBE partners.

4.5.1 PHOEBE's LinkedIn and Twitter accounts

LinkedIn and Twitter will be the project's primary social media outlets. All news items, events and other updates from the homepage are shared through both social media channels. Additionally, external content from the 'sister projects', interesting news items or studies, and related news from EU institutions are shared via these channels.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is a social networking website for professional development and is expected to attract an expert community of urban transport professionals to exchange on PHOEBE-related topics. Therefore, a dedicated PHOEBE LinkedIn page (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/phoebe-project/>) has been created, and LinkedIn Page analytics will be used to monitor the impact of communication on this channel. The selection of a 'company page' as the right tool to disseminate project content is due to the versatility of such a page, which also allows sharing of content by external users.

Twitter

Twitter is a helpful tool for sharing brief remarks, making announcements that can instantly reach a big audience, and retweeting relevant news. PHOEBE's Twitter account [@Project_PHOEBE](#) has been launched and is already making its presence.

The following hashtags have been identified to enhance the reach of the messages on social media: #roadsafety, #transportmodelling, #phoebeproject, #safemobility, #HorizonEU. In addition, PHOEBE's posts also tag the consortium partners' social media accounts and [@HorizonEU](#) to increase reach.

Figure 9 - PHOEBE LinkedIn and Twitter screenshots

4.6 Dissemination Material

In this context, dissemination material is defined as knowledge products and other resources that aim to share technical project results and knowledge about the PHOEBE Framework or any specific part of it. The following section explains the importance and uses cases of each material.

Videos

PHOEBE will produce two videos. The first video will be produced relatively early to introduce the project's aims, challenges and proposed solutions. The second video will be published towards the end of the cycle to summarise the research, tools and local achievements from the three pilot cities. Whereas the first video will be created and published in the project's first year, the second version will capture the results in the last six months. These videos, alongside the recordings of the webinars, will be uploaded on the **POLIS Youtube Account** in a dedicated playlist and embedded in the PHOEBE website.

Factsheets

Four factsheets will be produced that will highlight the methodology, present the pilot cities and summarise the achievements of the project.

Rollups & Leaflets

Three rollups will be produced, including information about the project, its partners, its aims and EU funding. The rollups will be made in the project's first months and will be distributed to the project coordinator, the dissemination task leader, and a third partner that requires it. The design, logos and colours will follow PHOEBE's visual identity (see section 4.1 Visual identity).

The leaflets are designed at the beginning of the project. After that, the leaflets will be made available in digital format, which allows partners to print material on a case-by-case basis. This process was agreed upon during the first consortium meeting in November 2022 to reduce paper waste and storage requirements, thus increasing sustainability.

4.7 Publications

PHOEBE will produce articles covering the project concept, ideas, expected impact, and project results. They will be made available through the consortium partners' channels, trade journals and popular press.

PHOEBE also aims to contribute to Open Research by publishing in open peer-reviewed scientific journals, magazines, book chapters, conference proceedings, and other publications¹. Projects under Horizon Europe funding must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications. PHOEBE's partners will disseminate the main project findings and innovations.

A non-exhaustive list of reference magazines, publications and journals that are of potential relevance for PHOEBE are:

Cities in motion, ELTIS, Cities Today, Traffic Technology International, Intertraffic World, ITS International, Transportation Research Record, Transportation Research Parts B and C; Transportation Research Part F: Traffic Psychology and Behaviour; European Journal of Transportation Research; Accident Analysis & Prevention; Journal of Safety Research; Journal of Transportation Safety and Security; IATSS Research; European Commission scientific publishing service (**Open Research Europe**).

¹ More information https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf and <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

5 Networking and Events

5.1 Cooperations with other projects

The two 'sister projects' of '**V4Safety**' and '**SOTERIA**' are at the centre of the project cooperation by PHOEBE. As previously indicated, both projects will be highlighted on a dedicated page on the PHOEBE homepage. In addition, the following aspects are planned in collaboration with 'V4Safety' and 'SOTERIA':

- Regular webinars:

Webinars are an efficient way of updating interested stakeholders about the projects' individual progress, highlighting commonalities and discussing the topic of 'road safety' from the different angles of each project. Webinars will take place on (at least) an annual schedule.

- Shared external speaking engagements:

If the topic, time and schedule allow, potential cooperation for speaking engagements related to the topic of road safety is sought. As an example, a joint application for a panel on 'road safety' aspects for international events related to urban mobility, industry gatherings and conferences shall be made (for further info, see section 5.2 Events).

- Promotion of content:

As mentioned in the sections about social media, newsletters and the homepage, PHOEBE aims to highlight results from the other two projects.

Since PHOEBE's partners are working on various EU-funded projects, certain synergies can be identified. For example, potential projects and respective communities with road safety aspects are (among others):

- **DIT4TraM:**
Stands for Distributed Intelligence and Technology for Traffic and Mobility Management. It offers an alternative decentralised approach, swarm intelligence, that helps local and bottom-up regulation.
- **TANGENT:**
Establishes establishing new technologies and services for transport systems managers, including travel behaviour modelling, traffic network prediction simulation models, transport network optimisation tools, and decision-making support tools like dashboards to enhance multimodal transport management
- **LEVITATE:**
Aimed to prepare a new impact assessment framework to enable policymakers to manage the introduction of connected and automated transport systems, maximise the benefits and utilise the technologies to achieve societal objectives.
- **iDREAMS:**
Sets up a framework for defining, developing, testing and validating a context-aware 'Safety Tolerance Zone' for driving within a smart Driver, Vehicle & Environment Assessment and Monitoring System (iDREAMS).
- **SAFE-UP:**
SAFE-UP aims to proactively address the upcoming safety challenges by developing innovative technologies, testing and assessment methods. SAFE-UP is based on 3 key pillars: i) future

safety-critical scenarios, ii) new safety technologies, and iii) novel safety assessment methodologies.

5.2 Events

European events, stakeholder meetings, conferences and symposia are perfect opportunities to engage with a broader audience of stakeholders from across the continent. Thanks to the long-standing expertise of the project partners, various tentpole events are scattered across the calendar year. To coordinate the (application for) speaking engagements, a list of events is located in the shared drive. Fortunately, road safety is a topic that has a significant potential to be discussed from different perspectives, including active mobility users (Walk21, ECF), road transport (IRF, IRU), Cities (POLIS Network), as well as from a technological perspective (ERTICO). These organisations organise an annual or regular conference, of which a (non-exhaustive) list of potential events is listed below.

Event name	Organiser	Target Group
Annual POLIS Conference	POLIS Network	Cities, EU institutions, Mobility Planners, EU project stakeholders
ITS Europe Congress	ERTICO	Technical experts, OEMs, Cities, Consultancies
Velo-City	European Cyclist' Federation	VRUs NGO and associations, Transport planners, National and local authorities, advocates, academics
Forum of European Road Safety Research Organisations	FERSI – Road Safety Research	City Authorities and Decision Makers
EURO Working Group on Transportation Meeting	National Research Council of Italy	City Authorities, Academics
European Researchers' Night event	European Commission	Academics, EU institution representatives
CIVITAS Urban Mobility Days	CIVITAS, POLIS Network	Organisations, NGOs, cities, EU projects
Walk21 Conference	Walk21	VURs NGO and Associations, National and local authorities, Mobility planners, academics
Automotive Week	City of Helmond & Dutch NGOs	Private sector
UITP Global Public Transport Summit	UITP	Public transport operators
Urban Future	City Changers	Organisations, NGOs, businesses
Conferences of road transport organisations: IRF, IRU, PIARC	International Road Federation, International Road Transport Union, World Road Association	Road transport, OEMs, Freight Forwarders etc.
IRAP Innovation Workshop	IRAP	Policymakers and road safety community

Table 4 - Non-exhaustive list of European and international events

Additionally, within the UN Global Road Safety Week framework NTUA organises a Scientific Workshop. It includes presentations of the main findings and challenges of key road safety research projects carried out within NTUA and involves discussion in a round table with high-level experts on key innovations in road safety research in Greece, Europe and worldwide. The next workshop will take place in 2023 and 2025, so PHOEBE work and results will be disseminated among other projects.

5.2.1 PHOEBE Events

Several events will be organised throughout the project's lifetime, including one dedicated webinar per pilot city and a final conference. Whereas the three webinars will be conducted online, and the recordings will be published on the POLIS Network Youtube Channel, the final conference will occur physically in the project's last months.

Final event

The final physical event will showcase the results and celebrate PHOEBE's achievements. All involved partners should have the chance to present their results in front of a mixed audience, which will be comprised of EU institution representatives, stakeholders, European city representatives, and technical and academic experts. The event will have a high-level characteristic and also potentially integrate the project results of the two sister projects of 'V4Safety' and 'SOTERIA'.

5.3 Multi-stakeholder engagement

PHOEBE has an interdisciplinary approach and therefore needs to engage with a variety of different stakeholders from different fields and expertise. In section 3.2, the main target groups for communication and dissemination purposes have been described. Engaging with these target groups will be done through the different channels and tools presented here and through the described events and other specific activities that will arise during the project's lifetime. The PHOEBE network also needs a group of external stakeholders to have an active role in ensuring the acceptance of the PHOEBE framework.

The first group of active external stakeholders will be made of relevant local stakeholders linked with the use cases, and it will be established under *Task 4.1: Stakeholder engagement and Area B alignment*. This task will cooperate closely with the tasks within WP6.

A second small group of external stakeholders will be established outside the use cases environments. This group will act as a sounding board for project work and findings, ensuring that the project ambitions and the end-users expectations are aligned. It should be a cross-disciplinary group, including road safety practitioners, transport planners, modelling experts, social and behavioural sciences practitioners, and other relevant stakeholders. Many stakeholders are already relevant to the project within the partners' networks, and PHOEBE will benefit from that to attract participants to the group.

This multi-stakeholder group is of critical relevance for the success of PHOEBE, its uptake and transferability. Having the validation and input of the external stakeholders will ensure that PHOEBE will reach and surpass its objectives. However, the group should focus mainly on a solid knowledge exchange culture and thus provide a setting similar to a Community of Practice (CoP). CoPs are groups that share common concerns and interests in a topic and come together for both individual and group goals. Hence, the multi-stakeholder group should work in reciprocity, and external participants should also benefit from participating. That implies that PHOEBE's consortium as a whole takes ownership of the group and actively engages with it, being attentive to challenging moments and open to exchanges and cooperation. POLIS will lead this task, but support and inputs from other partners are essential.

Participation in such a community for a long time (approximately 40 months) demands a level of commitment that might be hard for some stakeholders. Therefore, PHOEBE will have a more flexible approach to the multi-stakeholder group, being open to inviting other stakeholders that might be more

relevant to specific activities and that might be more readily available at particular moments. Once again, the engagement of PHOEBE's partners with the group is essential to ensure that the process is effective.

The group should not have more than ten stakeholders simultaneously, and they will provide support on tasks that demand end-user input and validation. For example, these tasks could be the methodology tasks from **WP1** (PHOEBE framework – methodological and technical approach), **Task 2.1** (Data needs analysis, consultation and requirement consolidation), tasks from **WP3** (Model development and enhancement for VRU and urban safety), and **Task 5.5** (Users interface and implementation). Meetings will be held both online and in person at least once a year in sync with the project needs and relevant milestones. The multi-stakeholder group will be established by M7 with its Terms of Reference that will detail tasks, procedures and commitments from PHOEBE's and the stakeholders' side.

6 Initial Exploitation Strategy

6.1 PHOEBE Exploitation Strategy in a nutshell

At the proposal preparation stage, the project partners have defined preliminary key exploitable results (KERs), which are summarised in the table below:

KER	Description	Owning Partners
KER 1	Predictive safety assessment theoretical and methodological framework	ALL
KER 2	Socioeconomic analysis model	TUM, TUD
KER 3	Traffic simulation safety module	AIM
KER 4	Dynamic road safety assessment models and tools	iRAP
KER 5	Urban road safety modelling knowledge product	iRAP
KER 6	Human behavioural modelling knowledge product	TUD, NTUA
KER 7	Mode shift and induced demand modelling knowledge product	TUM, NTUA
KER 8	Data capture and analysis techniques and processing toolchain	FLOW, FC, O7
KER 9	Use case analysis results and recommendations for Athens, Valencia and West Midlands	NTUA, FC, FLOW
KER 10	PHOEBE framework implementation guide and user support resources	ALL
KER 11	Publications, academic papers and user interface	ALL
KER 12	Databases containing use case mobility data and modelling results for Athens, Valencia and West Midlands	TUD, UPV

Table 5 - Preliminary Key Exploitable Results

The consortium intends to turn its participation and the project outcomes both into commercial exploitation (by building a strategy based on PHOEBE simulation module commercialisation, defining partnerships with industry leaders, licensing the technology to companies, or spinning off a start-up to bring the research to market) and to non-commercial exploitation (launching new R&I activities, thanks to the knowledge gained).

The core innovation of PHOEBE will be exploited as a predictive safety assessment framework methodology and its application, i.e. an integrated tool for the enhancement of road safety in urban areas. A step-by-step exploitation strategy will allow exploitation routes combining two kinds of plans:

- **Joint Exploitation Plan:** a common exploitation plan defined and implemented according to the position of each partner within the value chain and the existing background and foreground generated.
- **Individual Exploitation Plan:** each partner will build its individual exploitation plan according to its exploitation strategy and capacities.

Each partner will define its own targeted strategy to ensure that all results count towards a clear roadmap to reach a market uptake phase.

Overall, exploitation will be based on a common strategy, a set of actions and a plan to support key stages in innovation to create and exploit valued project outcomes, paying particular attention to preparing the ground for high impact at later stages.

6.2 IPR Elements definition – criteria

The IPR strategy will focus on protecting the project's results through patents and trademarks and ensuring that the project's partners have the necessary licences to use the results.

Elements of the solution to be intellectually protected will be classified as follows:

1. **Background:** elements or technologies used to build up the complete solution which has been entirely developed and owned by independent partners outside the scope of the PHOEBE project.
2. **Foreground:** elements or technologies used to build up the complete solution which have been developed, either independently or jointly with other PHOEBE's partners, once the project started and after they became part of the PHOEBE consortium.

6.3 IPR Ownership Identification – methodology

The owners of each of the elements will be identified in accordance with the following methodology:

- **Background contributions:** each PHOEBE's partner will be responsible for defining which background elements they have contributed to the solution. They will independently own these with the support of relevant evidence, as appropriate.
- **Foreground contributions and development:** partners will determine the share of their foreground IPR by identifying the proportion of the solution which they have developed, independently or in collaboration with other members of the consortium, and in a negotiation which will include all involved partners.

The consortium has defined the KERs that are considered the most vulnerable ones and will be considered with an ad-hoc perspective.

These KER can vary through time and are described as follows:

- KER 2 - Socioeconomic analysis model
- KER 4 - Dynamic road safety assessment models and tools
- KER 5 - Urban road safety modelling knowledge product
- KER 7 - Human behavioural modelling knowledge product
- KER 8 - Data capture and analysis techniques and processing toolchain

- KER 12 - Databases containing use case mobility data and modelling results for Athens, Valencia and West Midlands

6.4 Replication

Replication will be intended as the process of reproducing the project's results in other contexts or by sharing the project's methods, tools, and data with other researchers or organisations and supporting the replication of the project's results in other regions or countries.

The partners will agree upon the overall replication process.

7 Monitoring and partners' responsibilities

The dissemination and communication actions described in this deliverable will be monitored throughout the project to ensure their effectiveness and the necessary adjustments in case of any deviation. Table 7 and Table 8 describe PHOEBE's ambitions and target KPIs that will work as the base for monitoring the progress and impact of the project's dissemination and communication activities.

Based on the objectives, key messages, target groups, actions and KPIs for dissemination and communication presented throughout this deliverable, some responsibilities can be identified per partners. Table 6 gives an overview of responsibilities and contributions, and Table 7 Table 8 also specify the responsible and contributors partners per KPI. However, it is important to highlight once more that communication, dissemination and exploitation are a joint effort, and all the PHOEBE partners should engage in it.

Additionally, section 1.1 and Table 1 also identified the WPs responsible for the deliverables and milestones that demand extra effort and the partners involved are expected to contribute to the necessary communication and dissemination activities.

1. All partners
 - Share and promote the homepage, and social media channels with your network
 - @-tag PHOEBE in social media posts
 - Include homepage, social media and funding information in all dissemination materials
 - Contribute with relevant content for the new items and newsletters
 - Avoid using project-related language in written and spoken communication (e.g., work package, WP leader, tasks etc.)
2. Pilot site leaders (NTUA, FLOOW, FC, UPV, AIM)
 - Register (e.g. photos, videos) the interactions and events that take place locally
 - Provide regular updates about the progress at the pilot sites to populate the website section
 - Organise pilot site-specific webinars
3. Academic partners (NTUA, TUM, TUD, UPV)
 - Contribute and publish in scientific publications and conferences
 - Provide a simple-to-read summary of relevant academic publications and contributions for the website/news items
4. Non-profit organisations (POLIS, EIRA, IRAP)
 - Share updates about PHOEBE in your wide-network newsletters and events
 - Look for possible collaboration with other projects in their dissemination efforts
 - Include and advocate for PHOEBE as a topic in relevant working groups or task forces
5. Industrial partners (AIM, O7, FC, FLOOW)
 - Feature PHOEBE as a joint effort
 - Highlight the potential commercial benefits of the PHOEBE framework
 - Share updates about PHOEBE in your wide-network newsletters and events

Table 6 - Overview of partners' responsibilities and contributions

Target Group	Objective	Action Description	Indicator	Target	Responsible partner	Contributors
A, B, C, D, E	1, 2, 5	Scientific Conferences and international journals	Presentations at scientific conferences	Minimum of 4	NTUA, TUD, TUM, UPV	Other partners
			Peer-reviewed open-access publications during the project	Minimum of 8		
A, B, C, D	1, 2, 3	Participation in EU Events, trade fairs, Workshops	Presentation at events and reaching stakeholders	Minimum of 2 presentations during the project, and 1 after (POLIS Conference)	POLIS	All partners
				Minimum of 4 presentations (other events)	AIM, O7, FC, FLOW, EIRA, POLIS, iRAP	All partners
			Presentation in workshops and reaching stakeholders	Reaching a minimum of 200 cities, simulation developers and policymakers	EIRA, POLIS, iRAP	All partners
				Minimum of 1 workshop	EIRA, POLIS, iRAP	All partners
Reaching a minimum of 40 participants / workshop						
A, B, C, D, E	2, 3, 5, 6, 7	Clustering with similar EU-funded projects and related initiatives	Joint events, number of attendees	Minimum of 2 events, minimum of 20 attendees/event	Pilot site leaders (NTUA, FLOW, FC, UPV, AIM)	All partners
			Joint publications	2 publications	NTUA, TUD, TUM, UPV FLOW, FC, AIM	Other partners
All	1, 2, 3, 4, 6	PHOEBE Events	Final event, number of attendees	1 final event, minimum of 70 attendees	POLIS	All partners
			Webinars, number of stakeholders	Minimum of 3 webinars (min. 1 per use case), minimum of 30 stakeholders/event	Pilot site leaders (NTUA, FLOW, FC, UPV, AIM)	Other partners

Table 7 - Dissemination KPIs, respective target groups, objectives and responsible partners

Target Group	Objective	Action Description	Indicator	Target	Responsible partner	Contributors
All	1, 2, 3, 5, 6	Online presence: Project website and social media	Website	≥ 15,000 visits	POLIS	All partners
			Social media	≥ 500 followers and ≥1,000 mentions on the social media accounts	POLIS	All partners
A, B, D, E	1, 2, 3, 4, 6	Communication and promotional material	2 Videos	≥ 100 views/video	POLIS	Pilot site leaders, all partners
			7 Newsletters	100 new subscribers/year	POLIS	All partners
F	1, 2	Journalistic content: interviews, press releases, journalistic articles	5 Journal articles	≥ 5,000 readers reached via website, social media & multipliers	POLIS and Pilot site leaders (NTUA, FLOWW, FC, UPV, AIM)	All partners
			6 Press releases			

Table 8 - Communication KPIs, respective target groups, objectives and responsible partners

7.1 Dissemination Monitoring Tool

Another crucial tool to assess this strategy's effectiveness is the Dissemination Monitoring Tool. The tool is a live document created and shared by POLIS to keep track of the communication and dissemination activities done by the PHOEBE consortium. All the partners have the responsibility of updating the tool regularly, and information will be used for reporting in SyGMA.

This excel spreadsheet has two tabs, Communication and Dissemination activities and Publications, where partners can populate information such as events they attended, organisation of workshops, news items, conference publications, journal articles, and many others.

The monitoring tool is available on PHOEBE's Google Drive repository, and POLIS will send instructions and reminders as needed.

Last Update: 12/01/2022
By (name of partner): POLIS

PHOEBE Communication and Dissemination monitoring

Rules to follow when completing the Spreadsheet:

- Column A: Choose from the Drop-down menu one of 16 options which best corresponds to the dissemination activity. If you do not find an appropriate one, choose 'Other'
 - Column B: Specify your choice from column 1, especially if it is 'Other'. E.g. Column 1: Website --> Column 2: News article
 - Column D: Please enter the date in format 11/17/2018 (day/month/year)
 - Column F: Choose a category from the Drop-down menu. If there was a mixed audience of transport professionals, please select one category here and one more category in Column G. In rare cases choose 'Other', if no other category fits really suits.
 - Column G: Choose a category from the Drop-down menu in addition to the category of Column F.
 - Column H: Please, give an estimate of how many people approximately were at the event/visit the website, etc.
 - Column I: Please, give the exact name of the event, e.g. TRA Conference, you may also include the title of the presentation. For a publication, the exact name of the magazine, e.g. Cities in Motion Magazine, you may also include the title of the publication. For a news item the title of the newspaper, etc.
 - Column K: If available, always provide a link.
- As a general comment: **Please, do not list** here your contributions to the PHOEBE newsletter and website.

Reporting Table								
Type of dissemination activity	Dissemination Activity	PHOEBE participation (partners)	Date	Location	Type of Audience	2nd Type of Audience	Size of audience	Description
Organisation of webinar	POLIS Webinar	POLIS	01.01.2023	Online	(4) General Public	(4) General Public	50	Introduction webinar
Website	News article	IRAP	02.10.2023	Online	(3) Local/regional/national	(3) Civil Society	88 page views	Announcement release
Other	Newsletter	IRAP	21.12.2023	Email	(9) Local/regional/national	(3) Civil Society	15.000	IRAP Newsletter Wrap
Website	IRAP Partner Portal project listing	IRAP	02.10.2023	Online	authorities	(3) Civil Society	220	Key project details list

Figure 10 - PHOEBE Dissemination Monitoring Tool

8 Annex – PHOEBE Templates

Deliverable X.X

Name of deliverable

UK participants in Horizon Europe Project PHOEBE are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10038897 (The International Road Assessment Programme – iRAP) and 10056912 (The Flow)

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Project duration	<i>45 months</i>
Rights	<i>PHOEBE consortium</i>

PM efforts per beneficiary that contributed to the deliverable

#	Partner	PM effort in the Deliverable
1	<i>[Organisation name]</i>	
2		
3		
Total	<i>PHOEBE Consortium</i>	

Document History

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0.1	<i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>	<i>[Name, organisation]</i>	
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0.3	<i>DD/MM/YYYY</i>	<i>[Name, organisation]</i>	

Project Executive Summary

The EU-funded 'Predictive Approaches for Safer Urban Environment' (PHOEBE) project aims to develop an integrated, dynamic human-centred predictive safety assessment framework in urban areas. This will be achieved by bringing together the interdisciplinary power of traffic simulation, road safety assessment, human behaviour, mode shift and induced demand modelling and new and emerging mobility data.

Focused on vulnerable road users' safety, the 3.5-year-long PHOEBE project will draw inspiration from real-world scenarios in the three pilot cities of Athens (GR), Valencia (ES) and West Midlands (UK). Testing activities will be performed across the use cases to simulate and forecast the impact of changes on safety in different scenarios of disruptions or transitions across urban transport networks.

Predicting and visualising the safety and socioeconomic outcomes of new forms of transport, new technologies, or regulatory and behavioural changes from the individual (micro) level up to the network-wide (macro) level will also be a significant game-changer for urban stakeholders. The results of PHOEBE can be used as a blueprint by other European cities to develop their knowledge products, such as socioeconomic analysis model, urban road safety assessment, human behaviour and choice modelling.

PHOEBE pilot cities

List of participating cities:

- Athens (Greece)
- Valencia (Spain)
- West Midlands (United Kingdom)

Social Links:

https://twitter.com/Project_PHOEBE

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/phoebe-project/>

<https://www.youtube.com/@phoebeproject>

For further information please visit WWW.PHOEBE-PROJECT.EU

Project Partners

Organisation	Country	Abbreviation
EVROPSKI INSTITUT ZA OCENJEVANJE CEST - EURORAP	SI	EIRA
ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION	EL	NTUA
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITEIT DELFT	NL	TUD
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET MUENCHEN	DE	TUM
AIMSUN SLU	ES	AIM
POLIS AISBL	BE	POLIS
FACTUAL CONSULTING SL	ES	FC
UNIVERSITAT POLITECNICA DE VALENCIA	ES	UPV
OSEVEN SINGLE MEMBER PRIVATE COMPANY	EL	O7
THE FLOW LIMITED	UK	FLOW
INTERNATIONAL ROAD ASSESSMENT PROGRAMME	UK	iRAP

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Acronym	Meaning
ASAP	As Soon As Possible
B2B	Business-to-business
B2C	Business-to-Consumer
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
KoM	Kick-off Meeting
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
WP	Work Package
MS	Milestone

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Deliverable executive summary

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1.2 Structure of the deliverable and links with other work packages/deliverables

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1.3 Example of citation

Citation of a paper (X, 2018)

2 Title, subtitle and first chapter with content of deliverable

Title

Subtitle

Subtle emphasis

3 Header 1 (22 pt)

3.1 Header 2 (14 pt)

3.1.1 Header 3 (12 pt)

3.1.1.1 Header 4 (12 pt)

3.1.1.1.1 Header 5 (10 pt)

Standard (10 pt)

Emphasis

Intense emphasis

- List enumeration character 1

1. List numbering

Table Column title
Table Column body
Table Column body

Hyperlink

Followed hyperlink

Please use styles, fonts and font-dimension suggested by this template.
 For tables and graphs pick colours and related shades included in the palette of the theme.

	CMYK	RGB	HEX
	59/35/0/47	56/88/136	385888
	85/25/0/35	25/126/167	197EA7
	66/57/0/55	40/50/116	283274
	0/16/100/0	255/215/0	FFD700
	0/35/100/0	255/165/0	FFA500
	0/73/100/0	255/69/0	FF4500
	0/91/73/14	220/20/60	DC143C
	0/0/0/50	128/128/128	808080

4 Conclusions

Donec sociis scelerisque nec neque curae; class. Tincidunt ultrices eget purus cum nunc sagittis. Bibendum curae; ligula nullam ullamcorper sapien tempus mauris fames sollicitudin, turpis proin tempus. Feugiat potenti odio egestas pulvinar etiam aliquet Lacinia luctus mauris turpis nunc. Suspendisse non aliquam Eros cum, senectus primis convallis egestas commodo quis eleifend non turpis adipiscing elementum elementum sollicitudin sed duis tristique, tempor aptent sapien ridiculus ad maecenas.

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5 References

1. Author (2000). Title. etc.
2. Author (2000). Title. etc.
3. Author (2000). Title. Etc

For each reference, please choose the appropriate referencing style.

Journal

Author (Year). Title. Journal, Volume(Issue), (pp. page#-page#).

Book

Author (Year). Title (Edition). City: Publisher.

Book section

Author (Year). Title. In Editor name (Ed.), Book Title (Edition, pp. page#-page#). City: Publisher.

Conference paper

Author (Year). Title. Paper presented at the Conference Name, Conference Location. Retrieved from URL.

Web page

Author (Year). Title. Retrieved on Date from URL.

General

Author (Year). Title. In Secondary Author (Ed.), Secondary Title (Edition, pp. page#-page#). City: Publisher.

6 Annex

Donec sociis scelerisque nec neque curae; class. Tincidunt ultrices eget purus cum nunc sagittis. Bibendum curae; ligula nullam ullamcorper sapien tempus mauris fames sollicitudin, turpis proin tempus. Feugiat potenti odio egestas pulvinar etiam aliquet Lacinia luctus mauris turpis nunc. Suspendisse non aliquam Eros cum, senectus primis convallis egestas commodo quis eleifend non turpis adipiscing elementum elementum sollicitudin sed duis tristique, tempor aptent sapien ridiculus ad maecenas.

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Deliverable X.X

Name of Deliverable

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101076963

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What is PHOEBE?

- Lorem ipsum

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Pilot Cities

- Athens - Greece
- Valencia - Spain
- West Midlands - United Kingdom

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User Guide

PHOEBE

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Header 1 (Arial – 40 pt – Dark blue)

HEADER 2 (Arial – Min 20 pt / Max 36 pt – Orange)

- Body (Arial – Max 28 pt - Dark grey)
- List item 1
 - List item 2
 - List item 3 (Arial – Min 14 pt – Dark grey)

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Colour palette

RGB

56/88/136

255/215/0

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255/0/0

220/20/60

128/128/128

HEX

385888

FFD700

FFA500

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808080

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Table

Header 1	Header 1	Header 1	Header 1
Item 1	Item 1	Item 1	Item 1
Item 2	Item 2	Item 2	Item 2
Item 3	Item 3	Item 3	Item 3
Item 4	Item 4	Item 4	Item 4
Item 5	Item 5	Item 5	Item 5

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Images

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THANK YOU!

Project Coordinator

NAME – COMPANY - MAIL

Communication Manager

NAME – COMPANY - MAIL

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Meeting Name

Meeting Minutes

Date: XX/XX/XX

Meeting organizer: Partner name

Type of meeting: Internal / External

Note taker: Partner name

Minutes

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Title

Press Release

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Title

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